

Imaging Data Management Survey Report and Next steps

Velasquez, S.M.¹, Fletcher, G.², Burel, J-M.³, Parson, M.⁴, Swedlow, J.³, Hartley, M.¹, and Yoldas Kupcu, A¹.

¹ European Bioinformatics Institute, European Molecular Laboratory, Hinxton, UK

² Royal Microscopy Society, Oxford, UK

³ University of Dundee, Dundee, UK

⁴ King's College, London, UK

Introduction

An online survey was conducted to collect data on the needs and challenges of the UK bioimaging community on imaging data management. The aim was to identify critical skill gaps that will help tailor and deliver a training curriculum.

This survey constituted the first step in the DRI Skills Data Stewardship project. The overall aim of the project is to build image data stewardship skills, role recognition and career pathways for the UK community of research technical professionals (RTPs).

The survey was conducted using google forms and remained open to responses for one month between April to May 2025. It received a total of 46 responses from various imaging facilities and institutions across the UK.

The survey was advertised on three different mailing lists (BioImagingUK, volumeEM and EM-UK) and the BioImagingUK slack channel.

There were a total of 21 questions. The core team of the project Melina Velasquez, Aybuke Yoldas, Mathew Hartley, Georgina Fletcher, Jean-Marie Burel, Maddy Parsons and Jason Swedlow helped design the questionnaire.

The following questions were asked:

1. What type of biological imaging facility do you represent?
2. What imaging modalities does your facility have/use?
3. How is imaging data typically stored at your facility?
4. How is imaging data managed at your facility?
5. What metadata do you record at your facility?
6. If Other or None, please describe
7. How do you capture and record the metadata at your facility?
8. What metadata schema is used at your facility?
9. What file formats do you primarily use for imaging data?
10. Do you use ontologies or any kind of standard vocabulary to describe your data?
11. Does your facility have a dedicated data steward or data manager?
12. What are your biggest challenges in managing data prior to publication?
13. Does your facility deposit data in public repositories like the BioImage Archive and IDR?
14. What challenges do you face in depositing data in public repositories?

15. What improvements would make it easier for your facility to share data with public repositories?
16. What policies govern long-term data storage at your institution?
17. Do you need to share data with collaborators outside of your institution? If so, how do you go about it?
18. What type of support do you provide?
19. What type of training would benefit your facility most?
20. Are there any other challenges you would like to mention?
21. Is it ok to contact you for further information?

Analysis and Figures

For questions 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 8, 9, 11, 13, 16, 18 and 21, Google Forms created charts (Figs. 1-5, 8-9, 11, 13, 16, 18 and 21).

For other questions requiring text answers, word clouds were created to better see the commonalities between responses (Figs. 6-7, 10, 12, 14-15, 17, 19-20).

Questions 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 8, 9, 16, and 18 of the survey were designed as multiple-choice questions, while for questions 11 and 13 it was only possible to select one option. Questions 6, 7, 10, 12, 14, 15, 17, 19 and 20 were all free-text answers.

Word count percentages were calculated by calculating the number of responses that mention the word divided by the total rows in that given column (=question). This would mean a word percentage by respondent unless not all 46 respondents gave an answer to that particular question.

Question 21 contains the email addresses of the respondents who agreed to be contacted further. Therefore, that information is not made available in this report.

Figure 1. Bar chart corresponding to question 1 of the survey.

What imaging modalities does your facility have/use?

46 responses

Figure 2. Bar chart corresponding to question 2 of the survey.

How is imaging data typically stored at your facility?

46 responses

Figure 3. Bar chart corresponding to question 3 of the survey.

How is imaging data managed at your facility?

46 responses

Figure 4. Bar chart corresponding to question 4 of the survey.

What metadata do you record at your facility?

46 responses

Figure 5. Bar chart corresponding to question 5 of the survey.

What metadata schema is used at your facility?

46 responses

Figure 8. Bar chart showing the answers to question 8 of the survey.

What file formats do you primarily use for imaging data?

46 responses

Figure 9. Bar chart showing the answers to question 9 of the survey.

Figure 10. Word cloud showing the answers to question 10 of the survey ‘Do you use ontologies or any kind of standard vocabulary to describe your data?’

Does your facility have a dedicated data steward or data manager?

46 responses

Figure 11. Pie chart showing the responses to question 11 of the survey.

Figure 14. Word cloud showing the answers to question 14 of the survey ‘What challenges do you face in depositing data in public repositories?’

Figure 15. Word cloud showing the answers to question 15 of the survey ‘What improvements would make it easier for your facility to share data with public repositories?’

One takeaway point from the metadata question is the type and level of detail of the recorded metadata that the metadata that is recorded and the level of description largely depends on the user.

Another major issue is the lack of use of metadata schemas (not used by 85%) and ontologies (not used by 98%, though only 15 out of 46 . It bears significance to say that only 15 out of 46 respondents answered the ontologies question) (Fig. 8 and 10).

The majority of respondents use proprietary formats (70%) as image formats, closely followed by tiff (63%). Only 24% use OME-Tiff and 4% OME-Zarr (Fig.9). Overall very few use open-source cloud-friendly formats.

The majority of the challenges when handling data prior to publication are about overall data management: file location, lack of metadata, duplication of files (Fig.12). Most respondents (24%) reported large volumes of data as their biggest challenge, which links to problems with data storage (33%) and data transfer. In accordance, 59% of respondents said they lack a dedicated data steward or data manager to provide support in this matter (Fig.11). Understandably, this is reflected in the support the facilities provide. Most of the support provided at the institutions is on image acquisition (93%), processing (85%) and analysis (91%), whereas only 40% provide data management support (Fig.18). Training on data management was one of the main training needs voiced by the respondents, alongside image acquisition, processing/conversion and analysis (Fig.19).

When asked about, the majority of respondents indicated that they need to share data with collaborators outside of their institution, which incidentally came up as one of the biggest challenges in data handling in the previous question. The reported main ways of sharing are via external hard drives (54%), the cloud (41%), OneDrive (15%), Globus (15%), OMERO (6%) or some form of institutional file transfer system (Fig.17).

In addition to having problems with handling large volumes of data, other challenges not listed above were: data ownership, different requirements between repositories and also funders, limited staff and recognition, technical difficulties with formats, cost of data storage, lack of studies available for commercial re-use (Fig.12).

It becomes clear that more support is needed in order to have good standardization of (meta)data.

About 41% of the facilities publish the data in public repositories. The main reasons behind this low percentage seem to be lack of time, incentive, awareness, and support (Fig.13-14). This comes in contrast to the fact that most institutions are governed by institutional or funder long-term storage policies (Fig. 16) which usually mandate, or at least strongly encourage, the sharing of data within a certain time after the project has ended. However, it's worth noting that 35% of the respondents said there was no clear long-term storage policy (Fig.16).

Clear guidelines, policies, and universal standards were mentioned by a high proportion of respondents as being necessary to improve depositing data in public repositories (Fig.15). The lack of clear guidelines include those that come from the funders, as well as potentially the repositories themselves (though not explicit in all responses). There were 2 respondents mentioning some sort of monetary compensation would be needed to encourage researchers to share. Some respondents added training is needed to help with data deposition (Fig.15).

The majority of the respondents (67%) stated they had no standardised approach when asked how they manage imaging data at their facilities (Fig.4). This is highlighted in the answers to the question about their biggest challenges such as data location, lack of metadata, file duplication (Fig.12).

Next steps based on imaging data management needs survey

Based on the survey results, we propose to provide support and training for the following:

1. Imaging Data Management & Metadata in imaging
2. Imaging Data Storage, Transfer and Sharing
3. Public Repository Submission and Re-use
4. Train-the-Trainer Programme

1. Imaging Data Management & Metadata in imaging

The aim of this training module would be to improve the consistency and quality of imaging data management, and to support the adoption of metadata standards and FAIR principles.

We would plan to cover topics such as FAIR principles, use of metadata schemas, controlled vocabularies and ontologies to standardise metadata capture, organising and naming data, backup and version control, metadata throughout the data life cycle. It is important for the participants to have a clear understanding of the relevance of the data life cycle even before a project is started. Hence, we plan to teach about Data Management Plans (DMPs) and data management tools (OMERO, databases, ro-crate etc.).

One of the aims of this module is to help avoid situations of data loss and duplication. It would show the benefits of good data management practices when it comes to the transfer of projects or answering to reviewers. One of the take home messages is that good data management saves time in the long run and that it needs to be considered from the very beginning of a project. It would highlight how proper documentation of provenance of data is intricately tied to research integrity and reproducibility (by documenting every step of the way). Moreover, standardised data can be programmatically handled and analysed (AI-ready data), and is also easier to manage; especially for big or multi-modal datasets.

We plan to develop a workshop to cover the suggested topics, in addition to the already available materials like webinar series, documentation on ontologies and metadata schema for imaging data (from e.g. FoundingGIDE). We also plan to provide focused webinars, and set up consultations.

A potential workshop curriculum structure could be:

- I. What, when and how to capture metadata
- II. Standardised metadata: use of ontologies, and schemas like REMBI and MIFA

- III. How to store, manage and share metadata
- IV. Best practices and tools (incl. OMERO) in image data management
- V. Practical examples of FAIR

2. Image Data Transfer, Storage and Sharing

The expected learning outcome of this module would be to learn about data flow, what storage and sharing options there are, transfer tools like Aspera or Globus, and standardised file formats and conversion strategies.

We would aim to deliver training on the topics such as data flow, open and standardised file formats, file conversion, handling large files, data storage and sharing solutions tailored to imaging data. We also want to emphasize the importance of preserving raw data as well as processed data and analysis.

This module should prove attractive to our targeted audience, because once it is completed, participants should find it easier to handle and transfer large files and submit to repositories as an option to long-term storage of large files. In addition, they would be aware of easy ways to view and analyse large image data.

We plan to create training materials, and deliver workshops and consultations as part of the training resources for this module.

A potential workshop curriculum structure could be:

- I. Data flow
- II. Standardised data formats: open source cloud-friendly formats like OME-Zarr and conversion strategies
- III. Infrastructure (involvement of the IT department)
- IV. Remote visualisation and analysis of data

3. Public Repository Submission and Data Re-use

The purpose of this module is to convey the importance of sharing data and examples of data re-use.

We plan to cover topics such as FAIR open data (expanding on the difference between open data vs FAIR open data), the metadata required for submissions to public archives such as BIA and IDR, as well as archive policies such as licensing, and data retention.

This module should highlight the importance of meeting funder policies on data sharing, in addition to the personal benefits such as an increase of potential collaborations and citations. It would also highlight how submitting to public repositories could be an alternative solution to the problem of long-term data storage.

For this module, we plan to develop online tutorials for step-by-step guidelines on how to submit data. This means publicising existing ones and creating new ones if needed. We also plan to promote public sharing via the use of success stories.

A potential workshop curriculum structure could be:

- I. FAIR open data
- II. Advantages of using public repositories, i.e. funder policies, long-term storage, increased recognition and collaboration
- III. Thinking ahead: submission requirements
- IV. Submission tutorials
- V. Success stories and data re-use examples

4. Train-the-Trainer Programme

The aim of this final module is to train facilities staff as well as anyone who is interested in communicating the benefits of data management and data sharing. Therefore, we would be training future data stewards in imaging data. It is important to keep in mind that the ultimate target audience of the participants of this module are researchers and principal investigators.

Participants of this module should be able to transfer the following know-how to their audiences: encourage the development of internal data policies, and to clarify points like data ownership and access. They should be able to point to their institutional and funder policies on data management and release. They should be able to emphasise that good data records means good data provenance which is tied to research integrity and could avoid potential issues of reproducibility. In addition, they should be able to chase away certain common fears of data sharing, by explaining the career benefits and recognition. They should also exemplify the use of templates, and other tools using ontologies and schemas as ways to record and organise metadata collection and standardisation.

The new cohort of data stewards should be able to highlight how good data management practices save time in the long run (e.g. transfer of projects, answering to reviewers, etc), and meet funders requirements. It is also a way to avoid data loss and duplication.

For this module, we envision using material created for previous modules, as well as a dedicated workshop.

A potential workshop curriculum structure could be:

- I. Identify why researchers resist good data management practices and data sharing (time, difficult to do, lack of clear benefit)
- II. Identify what is important to them (publications, impact, reproducibility, saving time in the long run)
- III. Identify early adopters and data champions to showcase successful stories, and what could happen when you don't think about this
- IV. Useful metrics

Image Analysis (within the data life cycle)

Finally, as a side note, though the respondents to our survey mentioned image data analysis as a necessity, there are already existing courses and resources available on this topic provided by dedicated bioimage analysis communities. Therefore this project isn't planning to address image analysis by providing training, but its place in the data life cycle and integration of its metadata will be addressed in the relevant modules.

Annex

1. Imaging_survey_needs_raw_data